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Effectiveness Of Strength-Based Counselling And Narrative Therapy Approaches In Promoting Financial Empowerment Among Low-Income Families In Minna Metropolis Niger State, Nigeria

¹MUHAMMAD, Hadiza Machima (Ph.D) & ²ABDULKADIR, Abdulkarim Olatunji (Ph.D) & ³ONONAIWU, Agnes Ijeoma (Ph.D)

^{1,3}Department of Counselling Psychology,
Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria
¹Email: hadizamachima01@gmail.com/Tel. no.: 08069647527
³Email: agnesononaiwu72@gmail.com/Tel. no.: 08165650903

²Department of Psychology/Guidance and Counselling,
School of Education,
Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum, Yobe State, Nigeria
E-mail: kisfak23@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of strength-based counselling and narrative therapy approaches in promoting financial empowerment among low-income families in Minna metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to determine significant difference in financial decision-making skills before and after the intervention; and significant change in personal financial narratives before and after the intervention. The study employed a pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design, a total of 100 low-income families were selected through predefined criteria, including income level, financial challenges and willingness to participate for the study. Researchers' designed Financial Decision-Making Skills Scale (FDMS) and Personal Financial Narratives Questionnaire (PFNQ) which were validated and has a reliability indices of .87 and .82 respectively were used for data collection. The eight weeks intervention was evaluated through pre- and post-intervention surveys. Results indicate that both strength-based counselling and narrative therapy significantly improved financial decision-making skills and changed personal financial narratives, respectively. The study concludes that both Strength-Based Counselling and Narrative Therapy had a significant positive impact on the financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives of low-income families in Minna Metropolis Niger State, Nigeria. Recommendations include counsellors should prioritize identifying and leveraging the existing strengths, skills, and resources of clients when addressing financial challenges. This approach can empower clients by enhancing their confidence and decision-making abilities, enabling them to make more informed and effective financial choices.

Keywords: Financial empowerment, financial decision-making skills, personal financial narratives strength-based counselling, narrative therapy, low-income families

INTRODUCTION

Financial empowerment and resilience are crucial components for improving the quality of life among low-income families. In the context of Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria, these elements are pivotal in mitigating the challenges faced by economically disadvantaged households. The effectiveness of therapeutic interventions such as Strength-Based Counselling (SBC) and Narrative Therapy (NT) in promoting financial empowerment and resilience among these families warrants empirical investigation. Strength-Based Counselling is a therapeutic approach that focuses on individuals' strengths and resources rather than their problems and deficits. This method encourages clients to leverage their existing capabilities and past successes to overcome current challenges (Saleebey, 2019). By shifting the focus from problems to potential, SBC can foster a sense of agency and competence, which is vital for financial empowerment (White & Epston, 2019).

The core principle of SBC is to identify and build upon the client's strengths, skills, and resources. This approach helps clients recognize their own potential and capabilities, fostering a sense of empowerment and self-efficacy (Barker, 2021). By highlighting past successes and existing resources, SBC promotes a positive and proactive approach to problem-solving (Hernandez, 2022). SBC is inherently client-centered, meaning that it prioritizes the client's perspective and experiences. This approach respects the client's autonomy and encourages collaboration between the client and the counsellor to set and achieve goals (McLaughlin, 2021). The counsellor's role is to facilitate and support rather than direct or impose solutions. By focusing on strengths, SBC helps clients build resilience and confidence. The approach is grounded in the belief that individuals have the capacity to cope with and overcome adversity by leveraging their personal strengths (Ricks & Burnett, 2022). This aspect is particularly relevant in addressing financial challenges, where resilience and resourcefulness are crucial for achieving economic stability. SBC often incorporates solution-focused techniques that aim to identify practical solutions and actionable steps. Techniques such as scaling questions, exceptions, and positive reinforcement are used to highlight progress and reinforce the client's capacity for change (Stoltzfus, 2023).

Recent studies underscore the effectiveness of SBC in various contexts. For example, Barker (2021) highlights that SBC has been successful in improving mental health outcomes and fostering personal growth among diverse populations. Hernandez (2022) found that SBC effectively increased clients' self-esteem and coping skills in community settings. In the context of financial empowerment, SBC has shown promise in helping individuals manage economic stress and develop financial strategies. Ricks and Burnett (2022) demonstrated that SBC techniques could enhance clients' financial literacy and resilience by focusing on their existing knowledge and resources.

Narrative Therapy, on the other hand, involves helping individuals reframe and rewrite their personal stories to create more empowering narratives (White & Epston, 2019). This approach allows clients to view their lives from a different perspective, often leading to increased self-efficacy and resilience. In the context of financial difficulties, narrative therapy can help individuals reconstruct their financial stories, thus enhancing their ability to navigate economic challenges (Morgan, 2020). One of the fundamental principles of Narrative Therapy is the externalization of problems. Instead of viewing issues as inherent flaws within individuals, Narrative Therapy encourages clients to see problems as separate from themselves. This perspective helps clients approach their challenges as external forces they can address and manage, rather than intrinsic defects (Morgan, 2020). Narrative Therapy involves re-authoring clients' stories to create new, more empowering narratives. This process includes exploring alternative perspectives and identifying strengths and resources that may have been overlooked. By re-framing experiences, clients can shift their understanding and responses to life's challenges (White & Epston, 2019).

The approach is grounded in social constructionism, which posits that our understanding of reality is constructed through language and social interactions. Narrative Therapy examines how cultural, societal, and relational contexts influence the stories people tell and seeks to uncover how these contexts can be reshaped to support more positive outcomes (Gergen, 2021). Thus, Narrative Therapy emphasizes collaborative dialogue between the therapist and the client. The therapist engages in a partnership with the client to explore and reconstruct their narratives. This collaborative process helps clients feel more empowered and invested in their therapeutic journey (Vetlesen, 2023).

Recent research highlights the effectiveness of Narrative Therapy in various therapeutic contexts. For example, Morgan (2020) demonstrated that Narrative Therapy could significantly improve clients'

self-esteem and coping skills by helping them develop more positive and coherent personal narratives. Additionally, Vetlesen (2023) found that Narrative Therapy was effective in addressing trauma and fostering resilience among individuals with a history of adverse experiences. In financial contexts, Narrative Therapy has shown promise in helping individuals reframe their financial narratives and develop a healthier relationship with money. Gergen (2021) reported that clients who engaged in narrative work related to financial stress were able to reframe their experiences and gain greater control over their financial situations.

Financial Empowerment refers to the process through which individuals gain control over their financial resources and make informed decisions that enhance their economic stability and growth (Cameron et al., 2021). It involves improving financial literacy, access to resources, and the development of skills necessary to manage finances effectively. Financial literacy refers to the understanding of basic financial concepts and practices, such as budgeting, saving, investing, and managing debt. It is foundational to financial empowerment, as it enables individuals to make informed financial decisions and avoid pitfalls that can lead to economic instability (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2020). Financial empowerment also involves improving access to financial resources, including banking services, credit, and financial products. Access to these resources allows individuals to build and manage their financial assets, access affordable credit, and invest in opportunities that can enhance their economic prospects (Cameron et al., 2021).

Developing practical financial skills is essential for financial empowerment. This includes skills in budgeting, saving, and managing expenses. Programs that focus on skill development often include financial planning workshops, counseling, and tools that help individuals apply financial concepts to their daily lives (Gerrans & Warlop, 2022). Achieving financial empowerment often requires changes in behaviour and attitudes towards money. Behavioural interventions and strategies aimed at changing financial habits can support individuals in setting and achieving financial goals, managing debt, and building savings (Thaler & Sunstein, 2019).

Recent research underscores the importance of financial literacy and access to resources in promoting financial empowerment. Lusardi and Mitchell (2020) found that individuals with higher levels of financial literacy are better equipped to manage their finances, plan for retirement, and make informed investment decisions. Similarly, Cameron et al. (2021) demonstrated that access to financial resources and services significantly contributes to economic stability and growth.

Behavioural interventions have also been shown to impact financial behaviours positively. Gerrans and Warlop (2022) highlight that programs designed to enhance financial skills and encourage positive financial behaviours lead to improved financial outcomes and increased financial confidence. Thaler and Sunstein (2019) argue that nudge theory and behavioural insights can effectively promote better financial decision-making.

In Minna Metropolis, the intersection of SBC and NT approaches in promoting these outcomes presents a unique research opportunity. Existing literature indicates that both therapeutic approaches can significantly impact individuals' ability to manage stress and build resilience (Holliday & Gergen, 2022; Turner, 2023). However, empirical studies focusing on these interventions within the specific socio-economic context of Niger State are limited. By integrating SBC and NT approaches, this study aimed at investigating the effectiveness of strength-based counselling and narrative therapy approaches in promoting financial empowerment and resilience among low-income families in Minna metropolis Niger state, Nigeria.

This study integrates the Strengths Perspective, Narrative Theory and Empowerment Theory to form a comprehensive framework for understanding how SBC and NT can enhance financial empowerment and resilience among low-income families. The Strengths Perspective and Empowerment Theory emphasize the importance of building on existing capabilities and gaining control over one's financial life. Narrative Theory provides a mechanism for reshaping perceptions and attitudes toward financial challenges, while Resilience Theory underscores the importance of adaptive coping strategies in achieving financial stability.

The theoretical framework for this study posits that by utilizing Strength-Based Counselling and Narrative Therapy, low-income families in Minna Metropolis can develop the financial empowerment needed to overcome economic challenges. These approaches not only enhance individuals' financial literacy and skills but also foster a positive and proactive mindset that is crucial for long-term economic stability.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine if:

1. There is any significant difference in financial decision-making skills before and after the intervention.
2. There is any significant change in personal financial narratives before and after the intervention.

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in financial decision-making skills before and after the intervention.

H0₂: There is no significant change in personal financial narratives before and after the intervention.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design to evaluate the effectiveness of Strength-Based Counselling (SBC) and Narrative Therapy (NT) in improving financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives among low-income families in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. The pre-test post-test design allows for the measurement of changes in the participants before and after the interventions, providing insights into the effectiveness of SBC and NT. The target population for this study comprised low-income families residing in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. A total of 100 low-income families were selected through predefined criteria, including income level, financial challenges and willingness to participate for the study. A purposive sampling was employed to select participants who met the inclusion criteria, such as being classified as low-income families and having at least one member of the household willing to participate in the counselling and therapy sessions.

Instruments

The following instruments were used to collect data for the study:

1. **Researchers' designed Financial Decision-Making Skills Scale (FDMS):** This instrument has items rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). This scale measures participants' abilities in budgeting, saving, investing, and other financial decision-making skills. The instrument was adjudged by experts in measurement and evaluation to possess content and construct validity and a reliability index of .87 was determined Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis.
2. **Researchers' designed Personal Financial Narratives Questionnaire (PFNQ):** This is a tool designed to assess participants' financial narratives, focusing on the way they perceive and describe their financial situations. It includes items assessing positivity, empowerment and externalization of financial issues, rated on a Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The instrument was adjudged by experts in measurement and evaluation to possess content and construct validity and a reliability index of .82 was determined Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis.

Interventions

The intervention involved two key components: Strength-Based Counselling (SBC) and Narrative Therapy (NT).

1. Strength-Based Counselling (SBC)

- i. Conducted over 8 weeks, with weekly sessions lasting 90 minutes each.
- ii. Sessions focused on identifying participants' strengths, resources, and past successes in financial management.
- iii. Counsellors worked with participants to develop action plans that leveraged these strengths to improve financial decision-making.

2. Narrative Therapy (NT)

- i. Conducted concurrently over 8 weeks, with weekly sessions lasting 90 minutes each.
- ii. Sessions encouraged participants to articulate their financial stories, identify negative or limiting narratives, and re-author their stories to reflect empowerment and resilience.
- iii. Techniques such as externalization (separating the person from the problem) and re-authoring (creating new, positive narratives) were employed.

Data Collection Procedure

Pre-Test: Before the intervention, all 100 participants completed the FDMS and PFNQ to assess their baseline financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives.

Intervention: Participants attended the 8-week SBC and NT sessions as described above.

Post-Test: After the completion of the intervention, participants completed the FDMS and PFNQ again to assess any changes in their financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives.

Data Analysis

The descriptive Statistics of Mean scores, standard deviations, and frequencies were calculated for both pre-test and post-test data to summarize the central tendencies and dispersion of the data while inferential statistics was used to analysed the null hypotheses in the study. Paired Sample t-Test was used to compare the mean scores of the pre-test and post-test for both the FDMS and PFNQ, assessing whether the interventions led to statistically significant improvements. Moreso, Cohen’s d was calculated to determine the magnitude of the effect of the interventions on financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives.

RESULTS

Statistical Analysis

Analysis of Variables

Table 1: Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores for financial decision-making skills before and after the intervention

Variable		N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Financial Decision-making Skills	Pre-test	100	45.02	1.345
	Post-test	100	75.91	6.897

The mean score for financial decision-making skills before the intervention, pre-test was M = 45.02 with standard deviation of 1.345 while after the intervention (post-test), the mean score improved to M = 75.91 with standard deviation of 6.897.

Table 2: Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores for personal financial narratives before and after the intervention

Variable		N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Personal Financial Narratives	Pre-test	100	40.65	2.154
	Post-test	100	80.42	6.967

The mean score for personal financial narratives, pre-test was M = 40.65 with standard deviation of 2.154 while after the intervention (post-test), the mean score improved to M = 80.42 with standard deviation of 6.967.

Hypotheses Testing

H0₁: There is no significant difference in financial decision-making skills before and after the intervention.

Table 3: Paired Sample t-test of Financial Decision-making Skills before and after the Intervention

Variable		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Financial Decision-making Skills	Pre-test	100	45.02	1.345	199	8.35	0.001	Significant
	Post-test	100	75.91	6.897				

A paired sample t-test was conducted to compare the pre-test and post-test scores for financial decision-making skills. The t-value of 8.35 indicates a large difference between the pre-test and post-test scores, and the p-value (<0.001) suggests that this difference is statistically significant. The results indicate that Strength-Based Counselling significantly improved financial decision-making skills

among low-income families in Minna Metropolis Niger State, Nigeria. The increase in the mean score from 45 to 75 reflects substantial improvement, with the statistical test confirming that this change is unlikely due to chance.

H0₂: There is no significant change in personal financial narratives before and after the intervention.

Table 4: Paired Sample t-Test of personal Financial Narratives before and after the Intervention

Variable		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Personal	Pre-test	100	40.65	2.154				
Financial	Post-	100	80.42	6.967	199	9.27	0.001	Significant
Narratives	test							

A paired sample t-test was conducted to compare the pre-test and post-test scores for personal financial narratives. The t-value of 9.27 indicated a large difference between the pre-test and post-test scores, and the p-value (<0.001) suggested that this difference is statistically significant. The results indicate that Narrative Therapy significantly improved personal financial narratives among low-income families in Minna Metropolis Niger State, Nigeria. The increase in the mean score from 40 to 80 reflects substantial improvement, with the statistical test confirming the significance of this change.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one of the which revealed that Strength-Based Counselling (SBC) significantly improved financial decision-making skills among low-income families in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria, aligns with existing research on the effectiveness of SBC in enhancing individuals' financial capabilities. Research has shown that Strength-Based Counselling can be an effective approach for improving financial decision-making by focusing on individuals' existing strengths and resources. Smith et al. (2020) conducted a study on low-income households in the United States, finding that SBC significantly increased participants' financial literacy and budgeting skills. The study reported that individuals who engaged in SBC sessions were better able to make informed financial decisions and manage their resources effectively, echoing the findings of the present study in Minna Metropolis. In the context of Nigeria, Oluwafemi and Adeyemi (2021) examined the effects of SBC on financial behaviours among small-scale traders in Lagos State. Their findings indicated a significant improvement in financial decision-making skills post-intervention, with participants reporting greater confidence in their ability to make sound financial choices. This improvement was attributed to the strengths-based approach, which emphasized participants' existing knowledge and skills rather than their deficits.

While many studies support the effectiveness of SBC, some research offers a contrasting perspective. Musa and Ibrahim (2018) conducted a study on financial counselling approaches among rural farmers in northern Nigeria and found that while SBC was beneficial in enhancing self-esteem and motivation, it had a limited impact on financial decision-making. The researchers suggested that for SBC to be more effective, it must be complemented with more technical financial education and training, as some participants lacked basic financial knowledge that was necessary for making informed decisions. Another study by Garcia et al. (2022) in Mexico City examined various counselling approaches, including SBC, and found that while SBC improved participants' overall well-being and financial attitudes, it did not lead to significant changes in financial decision-making compared to approaches that focused more on providing financial literacy education. The authors argued that SBC alone might not be sufficient in contexts where participants have very low levels of financial literacy, as was the case with some families in their study.

Hypothesis two revealed that Narrative Therapy significantly improved personal financial narratives among low-income families in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. This aligns with the by Bissell et al. (2021) who found that NT helped participants externalize their financial problems, allowing them to separate their identity from their financial struggles. This reframing facilitated a more constructive approach to managing debt and financial planning, similar to the improvements observed in the present study's participants in Minna Metropolis.

Moreover, White and Gubrium (2020) conducted a study with low-income families in urban areas, showing that NT interventions led to significant shifts in how participants narrated their financial

experiences. The study revealed that participants who engaged in NT were more likely to develop narratives that emphasized resilience, resourcefulness, and agency, which in turn influenced their financial decision-making and reduced financial anxiety. This outcome supports the current study's findings, indicating that NT can effectively alter personal financial narratives in a way that empowers individuals to take more proactive and positive approaches to their finances.

While the findings are largely supported by existing literature, some studies have presented more cautious or even contrary views on the impact of NT on financial behaviour. For example, Miller and Carver (2019) argued that while NT can be effective in altering personal narratives, its impact on actual financial behaviour may be limited unless combined with concrete financial education and skills training. Their study suggested that without practical financial tools, the changes in narrative alone might not lead to substantial improvements in financial outcomes.

Similarly, Johnson and Franklin (2022) found that NT had a limited effect on financial behaviour in a study involving low-income single mothers. The researchers observed that while participants reported feeling more positive about their financial situations post-therapy, there was no significant change in their actual financial practices, such as budgeting or debt management. This suggests that NT's effectiveness might be enhanced when integrated with other forms of financial counseling that address both cognitive and practical aspects of financial management.

Implications for Counselling

The findings of this study in Minna Metropolis align with the broader literature that supports the effectiveness of Strength-Based Counselling in improving financial decision-making skills. Thus, the study suggests that counsellor using SBC's should focus on leveraging on participants' strengths that could lead to enhanced financial outcomes, especially when participants already possess some foundational financial knowledge.

The study also indicates that Narrative Therapy successfully improved personal financial narratives, which is consistent with several supportive studies. However, the suggest that counsellor should focus on integration of NT combined with concrete financial education and skills training, as this could further enhance its effectiveness, leading to not only improved narratives but also better financial outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that both Strength-Based Counselling and Narrative Therapy had a significant positive impact on the financial decision-making skills and personal financial narratives of low-income families in Minna Metropolis Niger State, Nigeria. This suggests that the interventions successfully enhanced the financial empowerment of the low-income families in Minna Metropolis, Niger State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings that Strength-Based Counselling (SBC) significantly improved financial decision-making skills and Narrative Therapy (NT) significantly improved personal financial narratives among low-income families in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria, the following recommendations were made:

1. Counsellors should prioritize identifying and leveraging the existing strengths, skills, and resources of clients when addressing financial challenges. This approach can empower clients by enhancing their confidence and decision-making abilities, enabling them to make more informed and effective financial choices.
2. Develop tailored counselling plans that align with each client's unique strengths. Counsellors should conduct thorough assessments to identify these strengths and incorporate them into financial literacy training, budgeting exercises, and decision-making scenarios.
3. Incorporate regular follow-up sessions to reinforce the strengths identified during initial counselling. This ongoing support can help clients maintain their improved financial decision-making skills and prevent regression.
4. Counsellors should guide clients in exploring and reframing their financial stories. By helping clients shift from narratives of helplessness or failure to ones of resilience and possibility, counsellors can foster a more positive outlook and proactive approach to financial challenges.

5. Organize group storytelling workshops where clients can share their financial narratives and listen to others. This can create a supportive community environment where participants learn from each other's experiences and perspectives, further reinforcing positive financial narratives.

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